

EVALUATING MOTIVATIONS AND OUTCOMES IN CONSERVATION TRANSLOCATIONS

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CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1. INTRODUCTION	6
2. METHODS	10
3. MOTIVATIONS AND OUTCOMES OF CONSERVATION TRANSLOCATIONS: AN EXPANDED FRAMEWORK	12
4. APPLYING THE FRAMEWORK	20
5. EVALUATING OUTCOMES	26
6. LEARNING AND SHAPING NEW CONSERVATION POLICY AND PRACTICE	30
7. CONCLUSION	32
8. REFERENCES	33

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Conservation practice increasingly employs translocations (the human-mediated movement of living organisms) to address acute biodiversity challenges. While current guidelines for conservation translocations provide robust frameworks for their ecological and technical implementation, when it comes to human and social dimensions, they predominantly focus on stakeholder consultation and impact mitigation. This report proposes a new framework for systematically evaluating the broader human dimensions of conservation translocations, from conception through to evaluation. It identifies how identification of clear motivations – which are predominantly ecological, but often also shaped by other factors – can be linked to specific aims and intended outcomes and holistically evaluated.

The framework emerged through structured workshops and discussions of the People and Conservation Translocations (PaCT) network, comprising 23 participants including academic researchers, conservation practitioners, and policy advisors. Workshop activities focused on identifying non-ecological motivations for translocations and their diverse associated outcomes. The framework identifies four key categories of motivation, which collectively shape translocation projects:

- Ecological factors that inform species selection and conservation priorities
- Political and strategic factors that influence project support and implementation
- Socio-cultural factors that affect community relationships and cultural values
- Economic factors that impact recipient communities and stakeholders

These motivations are underpinned by ethical principles, affective responses, and philosophical perspectives about human-nature relationships. The report includes several case studies that demonstrate how failure to acknowledge these non-ecological influences can lead to project complications or failure.

The report provides a framework for understanding and clarifying different types of motivation and proposes systematically linking appropriate motivations to project aims (i.e., intended outcomes). The same framework can then be used to identify and evaluate non-ecological outcomes throughout a project's lifecycle. The report also provides a comprehensive list of methodological approaches that can be employed to identify and evaluate motivations and outcomes.

1. INTRODUCTION

Conservation translocations are human-mediated movements of living organisms from one area to another that provide quantifiable conservation benefits from population to ecosystem levels (IUCN/SSC 2013).

Conservation translocations include population restorations such as reinforcements and reintroductions within indigenous or historical ranges, and population introductions such as assisted colonisations and ecological replacements.

The latter comprise releases of organisms outside their indigenous ranges to prevent extinction and/or re-establish ecological functions lost through the extinction of similar species. As a conservation technique, translocations are increasingly carried out globally in response to current acute biodiversity challenges (Gaywood 2024; Seddon and Redford 2025). Conservation translocations are also fundamentally human endeavours with variable and sometimes complex motivations and outcomes. They are not always, or entirely, driven by ecological need or systematic prioritisation, and their effects may reach well beyond quantifiable ecological benefits. Translocations both depend on and have implications for the social and economic systems in which they are implemented. Nevertheless, the human social dimensions of translocations remain under-acknowledged, assessed, reported, and evaluated (Consorte-McCrea et al. 2022; Dando et al. 2023; Marino et al. 2024b).

This report proposes a new framework for understanding the human social dimensions of conservation translocations, from conception to evaluation. It highlights that in addition to ecological justifications and outcomes, there also exist a wider range of social, political, cultural and practical motivations for, and outcomes of, conservation translocations. The report signposts best practice guidance for acknowledging and accounting for these wider considerations in project development, delivery, and evaluation. This framework is designed to be complementary to current IUCN Guidelines for Reintroductions and Other Conservation

Translocations (IUCN/SSC 2013), IUCN Guidelines on Human-Wildlife Conflict and Coexistence (IUCN 2023), and national guidelines such as the Scottish Code for Conservation Translocations (National Species Reintroduction Forum 2014) and Reintroductions and other Conservation Translocations: code and guidance for England (DEFRA 2021). These existing guidelines all include social dimensions of translocations to varying degrees. They generally focus, however, on stakeholder consultation and engagement and/or impact mitigation (Glikman et al. 2022; Gaywood and Stanley-Price 2022). Indeed, there is increasingly good evidence and useful guidance on delivering these particular stages of translocation projects effectively, even if this is not consistently followed (Dando et al., 2021). This report complements this existing work by outlining how non-ecological considerations might additionally be usefully incorporated into the first (planning) and final (project evaluation) stages of a translocation project, thus contributing to the thinking and development needed for further 'formalised' guidance in this direction.

IUCN Guidelines state that conservation translocations *"must be intended to yield a measurable conservation benefit at the levels of a population, species or ecosystem, and not only provide benefit to translocated individuals"*. In practice, however, motivations for conservation translocations are often multidimensional since conservation projects, including translocations, are human initiatives driven not only by ecological goals, but also political, socio-cultural, and economic ones, all of which are informed by ethical, affective, and philosophical factors. While conservation justifications and ecological aims are fundamental to most conservation translocations, and are normally made explicit in project design, other motivations often remain unacknowledged.

This can lead to several related problems:

1. Translocation projects may be treated and communicated as apolitical, technical endeavours, failing to acknowledge that they are manifestations of particular ideas about how an environment should be, reflect choices as to what is classified as native or belonging, and potentially exclude alternate framings and definitions;
2. Ignoring these socio-political dimensions can result in inability to fully and transparently explain and justify projects, or failure to recognise their potential political or cultural implications;

3. Ultimately, where social dimensions have not been appropriately assessed and addressed, this can lead to negative outcomes including breakdowns of trust and relationships, uneven distribution of costs and benefits, and/or project failure.

Cases 1 and 2 detail two European examples of scenarios in which greater consideration of non-ecological motivations and outcomes of translocation projects would have been beneficial.

CASE EXAMPLE 1: REINTRODUCTION OF SAKER FALCON *FALCO CHERRUG* IN BULGARIA

The reintroduction of the Saker falcon was first reported as part of the Global Reintroduction Perspectives published in 2010 (Ragyov et al. in Soorae 2010). The reintroduction aimed to establish a self-sustaining breeding population in the country while also promoting wider conservation awareness and building capacity of conservation organisations in Bulgaria. However, the project encountered difficulties when some of the conservation NGOs were reluctant to cooperate, reportedly due to funding having originated from the Environmental Agency of Abu Dhabi, a nation with a history of falconry. The project was therefore perceived, by some, to be biased towards falconry interests, when thefts for falconry had been a key driver of the Saker falcon's extinction in Bulgaria (Ragyov et al. in Soorae 2010; Lazarova et al. 2021). Conservation NGOs were also cautious and isolated due to competition for funding in the socio-economic context of this former communist country. Furthermore, there was a certain level of opposition to the project since this type of conservation measure was not listed in the European Union Single Species Action Plan for Saker falcons at the time. Overall, this shows the importance of understanding and clarifying motivations from the outset of a translocation, including recognising differences within the broader conservation community, and understanding the wider socio-political context.

CASE 2: TRANSLOCATION OF BROWN BEARS *URSUS ARCTOS* IN ITALY

The translocation of brown bears from Slovenia to Trentino, Italy, highlights the need to account for different time scales between ecological and social outcomes. The translocation took place between 1999 and 2001 and sought the recovery of the relict and functionally extinct population of brown bears in Central Alps that consisted of three individuals, of which at least two were males. In ecological terms, the reinforcement quickly became a success. Thanks to a remarkably high growth rate, the population reached a viable size within the first decade following the reintroduction programme (Tosi et al. 2015). In the longer term, however, the population increase has led to a series of human-bear incidents, from minor injuries to a mushroom collector in 2014 to two attacks on joggers in 2023 and 2024 (the former fatal) (Groff et al. 2024). After the first incident in 2014, local attitudes and public opinion started shifting away from the initially positive response (Tosi et al. 2015). Although the programme has revisited social dimensions since its original feasibility study, this case study stresses the necessity of considering how management strategies might address unintended social outcomes even well after the release stage, and throughout changes of project ownership and management. This case also raises important questions about governance of translocated species: following an ecologically successful project, for how long do those delivering the translocation retain responsibility for the reintroduced population's subsequent effects on people and ecosystems?

Most examples in this report relate to mammals and birds, which are often the focus of both conservation initiatives and their controversies. However, social considerations are potentially relevant across all taxa. In the UK, some translocation projects have struggled due to unfavourable perceptions of translocated species. For example, lack of popularity, perception of nuisance, and affective responses (such as revulsion) have hindered engagement activities for translocated narrow-headed ants *Formica exsecta* (Carroll 2022). Concerns about environmental management practices associated with reintroductions, rather than the species itself, have also challenged translocation programmes. The potential need for land use restrictions limited stakeholder collaboration in translocations of small cow-wheat *Melampyrum sylvaticum* (Dalrymple et al. in Soorae 2008), and there was stakeholder opposition to fencing required for the release site of a reintroduction of field crickets *Gryllus campestris* (Sears et al. in Soorae 2021). The success of invertebrate translocations has also been affected by human factors, such as disturbance due to public interest in chequered skippers *Carterocephalus palaemon* at their release sites (Wells and Heydon 2022) and the recreational use of beaches hosting translocated mottled grasshoppers *Myrmeleotettix maculatus* (Gardiner, in Soorae 2011).

The following section of this report provides an outline of the background of the People and Conservation Translocations Network and the method employed to develop this framework. We then provide a diagram and detail of the expanded framework for assessing motivations, aims, and outcomes of conservation translocations. Finally, we work through the key stages of a translocation and identify how this framework may be usefully applied at each stage.

2. METHODS

This report is the primary output of a workshop held by the People and Conservation Translocations (PaCT) network in June 2023. The PaCT network, hosted by the University of Exeter's Environment and Sustainability Institute, is a collective of academic researchers, practitioners, and policy experts with shared interests in the human and social dimensions of conservation translocations.

The PaCT network was initiated by academic researchers affiliated with the University of Exeter, who first convened in February 2023 to identify current challenges and research gaps relating to social aspects of conservation translocations. Through structured discussion, this group identified that, while significant advances have been made in understanding how best to engage affected communities and stakeholders in conservation translocations, there is currently little assessment of translocation projects as socio-political projects in themselves. Specifically, the group highlighted the need for making explicit what is often tacit in conservation planning, by enabling greater recognition and discussion of a range of motivations and potential outcomes of conservation translocations, beyond ecological goals.

In June 2023, the UK PaCT network was established and met for the first time at the University of Exeter's Cornwall Campus for a two-day workshop focusing on non-ecological motivations and outcomes for conservation translocations. The 23 attendees of this workshop included academic researchers, conservation practitioners, and representation from Natural England and NatureScot (the licensing and advisory bodies for translocations in England and Scotland) and members of the IUCN specialist groups (the IUCN SSC Conservation Translocation Specialist

Group produces international guidance on wildlife translocations). Recognising that the majority of social research into conservation translocations to date has focused on stakeholder engagement, social feasibility, and conflict management, the workshop aimed to specifically focus on identifying and discussing how social factors were also relevant for understanding the motivations and outcomes of conservation translocations. Participants heard four applied examples of translocation projects and took part in structured activities and discussions. Day 1 focused on identifying motivations for conservation translocations beyond core ecological examples, and discussing how these might be better accounted for in project planning. Day 2 focused on identifying and evaluating non-ecological outcomes from conservation translocations.

Data from the workshop was collected on flipchart paper, sticky notes, and by a dedicated note-taker. Following the workshop, FM collated and summarised the outputs with input from SC. This formed the basis of the framework and first draft of this report. All members of the PaCT network were then asked to provide feedback on the framework and report. Following an online meeting to discuss comments and proposed changes, a final version was produced through iterative reviews and contributions of PaCT network authors.

3. MOTIVATIONS AND OUTCOMES OF CONSERVATION TRANSLOCATIONS: AN EXPANDED FRAMEWORK

We propose a new framework (Figure 1) that is designed to enable practitioners to evaluate three connected dimensions (motivations, aims, and outcomes) of translocation projects more holistically and systematically.

We propose that newly conceived or proposed projects are robustly interrogated in terms of its motivations (Figure 2). Motivations are the factors that have caused a project to be proposed in the first place, and though it is often assumed that these are largely, if not solely, ecologically oriented, this is not always the case. *Motivations* may or may not translate directly into project aims. Aims are the specific objectives of the project. These should be constructed around a core set of agreed-upon motivations and clearly linked to intended, and ideally measurable, outcomes. *Outcomes* are the effects or impacts of a project, including, but not limited to, ecological outcomes. Outcomes, both intended and unforeseen, can also be classified using the framework below, and evaluated accordingly.

The categories in this framework are not mutually exclusive, and some factors may belong to multiple categories. The factors are conceptualised as Ecological (generally the primary motivation for conservation translocations), Political and Strategic, Socio-Cultural, and Economic. Underpinning these are broader ethical principles, philosophies, affective drivers and personal enthusiasms. These components are described, with examples, in more detail below.

Figure 1. Expanded framework for assessing motivations, aims, and outcomes of conservation translocations, with examples.

3.1. Ecological

Ecological outcomes are central to the concept of conservation translocations, and existing guidance expects the ecological aims of any project to be explicitly stated. Nevertheless, this category also has important social dimensions that should be acknowledged.

Motivations: Species might be selected or prioritised because of their local or global rarity, the need to preserve or restore certain biological traits, and/or specific ecological dynamics and processes. These prioritisations are often generated from scientific research including data collection, analysis, and communication, which is itself a social process shaped by, for example, the interests and expertise of those involved; funding availability; and availability/accessibility of data. There are evident biases in the taxonomic groups and species targeted for conservation translocations that reflect wider conservation biases towards large-bodied, charismatic vertebrates (Seddon et al. 2005; Bajomi et al. 2010). Ecological motivations also include translocations carried out as trials or experiments in methodology and impact evaluation.

Outcomes: As conservation translocations are primarily intended to deliver ecological outcomes, these are covered in much greater depth elsewhere and will only be briefly reviewed here. Translocation aims can be targeted at both the population and species level (i.e. establishing a self-sustaining population) and relate to both immediate and long-term intended outcomes for the recipient ecosystems. For example, species recovery can also promote ecosystem restoration (e.g. through trophic cascades).

Translocations can also, however, result in unintended negative ecological outcomes such as biodiversity loss through interspecific competition (Novak et al. 2021) and pathogen introduction (Sainsbury and Carraro 2022; Mitchell et al. 2022) if appropriate methods and mitigation are not built into the project design. Perhaps a more likely risk, however, is that expected ecological benefits will simply not materialise, or be difficult to evidence.

3.2. Political and Strategic

As conservation translocations are environmental interventions practised by organisations and institutions with a range of broader goals, strategies and ideologies, there are often strategic or political factors that cause certain projects to be proposed and supported above others, or indeed dismissed as unrealistic. Political and strategic motivations are often unstated (except perhaps internally), but a lack of transparency about these factors can lead to distrust and conflict.

Motivations: Political and strategic motivations are those which employ translocations as a means to achieve broader aims than the specific ecological outcomes covered above. These motivations can be an important driver of conservation translocations at multiple levels. Local and national governments might commission or support translocations in response to internal motivations to meet policy commitments, advance a conservation strategy, or generate support and positive publicity. Similarly, charitable organisations might use high-profile translocations strategically to generate funding, visibility, and support, or to rebrand themselves. Political motivations can also be *external* as governments seek to meet commitments to international agreements (e.g. the Convention on Biological Diversity), legal obligations, and public priorities. Organisations might make similarly strategic decisions to take advantage of external opportunities, e.g. as time-limited projects featuring charismatic species might be considered attractive to funders (Marino et al. 2024b).

Outcomes: Accordingly, political outcomes include translocations contributing to meeting regulatory commitments and biodiversity targets, producing policy or legislative change, and/or boosting the reputation of organisations and individuals. Longer-term, successfully completed translocations may inspire institutional or governmental support for continuing programmes or new initiatives, perhaps reflected by the presence of champions in councils or parliaments. Translocations can also produce new connections between practitioners and researchers, for example in the form of specialist groups, and

collective learning could further improve practices. However, political outcomes might also include new or reignited conservation conflicts at local and national levels (Drouilly and O’Riain, 2021). Failed translocation initiatives may reduce political and/or public will to support future endeavours, with the individuals, organisations and institutions involved experiencing reputational damage and loss of funding support.

3.3. Socio-Cultural

Socio-cultural motivations form a broad category that recognises that conservation translocations can also be implemented to bring benefits to people, and because of (or to strengthen) relationships between individuals, communities and the species and landscapes in question.

Motivations: Translocations have been proposed as a means of restoring (or creating) natural heritage and cultural identity, particularly when a target species has symbolic value, forms part of traditional or religious practices, or is associated with specific places. Translocations of charismatic species have also been promoted as a means of connecting local and wider communities with nature and wildlife (White et al. 2023), or generating public interest in a particular species or habitat.

Outcomes: Translocating species might restore cultural practices, shape new ones, and/or contribute to renewed cultural connections with translocated species. Translocated species can therefore become socially accepted, culturally valued, and acknowledged as belonging within a socio-ecological system, thus reshaping sense of place. On the other hand, translocated species can also become disruptive elements within socio-ecological systems as seen with reintroduced wood bison *Bison bison athabasca* in Yukon disrupting Champagne and Aishihik First Nations’ traditional practices such as berry picking and trapline hunting either directly, through trampling, or indirectly, through damage caused by bison hunters (Clark et al. 2016).

Socio-cultural outcomes also include how translocations shape relationships between individuals and organisations. Positive outcomes might include new collaborations forming around species conservation (e.g. translocation fora, advisory groups), or increased ownership, stewardship, and accountability among local stakeholders. For example, an international and cross-cultural partnership between indigenous Winnemem Wintu (Middle Water People) of California, and Māori of Aotearoa New Zealand, has developed with the aim of ‘repatriating’ threatened Chinook salmon *Oncorhynchus tshawytscha* to reestablish a population in the McCloud River (Houck 2019). Translocations might also shape new senses of community and engender interest and engagement in conservation.

Translocations may build or damage trust and enable or hinder communication and collaboration, including for wider conservation initiatives beyond the translocation project. Given the right conditions and processes (e.g. meaningful stakeholder engagement), social learning can take place as a result of translocations. This means that relational and cognitive changes (e.g. understanding of others’ values) occur beyond the individual and spread through social interactions. How translocations and translocated species are narrated or portrayed by traditional and social media is an outcome over which project managers may have little control, but can nevertheless amplify or nullify other socio-cultural outcomes.

Finally, translocations may produce human health-related outcomes by improving, or worsening, people’s health and well-being. In theory, translocations can enable exposure to enriched biodiversity and access to nature that, through psychological and physiological mechanisms, can raise levels of stress recovery and mood, resistance to diseases and neuropsychiatric disorders, and activities in natural environments (van den Berg et al. 2007; Aerts et al. 2018; Methorst et al. 2021; Wong and Osborne 2022). Conversely, translocations may affect human well-being and health by disconnecting people from nature because of fear and stress related to negative experiences and impacts (even if only anticipated), and unpredictably changing microbial and disease-risk landscapes.

3.4. Economic

Conservation translocations hold increasingly recognised economic implications, as they may entail risks and opportunities for individuals and local communities.

Motivations: Economic motivations include the potential for translocations to generate income (through ecotourism, project-related employment, land, and resource value change), or be employed as ‘Nature-based Solutions’ to economic challenges. Economic interests are also relevant to project motivations when species are intended for direct use as a resource and can be a key area in which conservation and game interests align, e.g. in support of translocations of elk *Cervus canadensis* in Tennessee (Chapagain and Poudyal 2020) and black grouse *Lyrurus tetrix* in England (Warren and Baines 2018).

Outcomes: Translocations can produce both economic benefits and losses. These might be direct, such as income generated through ecotourism (Auster et al. 2020a) and opportunities for marketisation (e.g. species-themed festivals such as ‘FestiVOLE’ in England, celebrating water vole reintroduction, and the ‘Eagle Town’ initiative of the South of Scotland Golden Eagle project). Outcomes might also be indirect, in terms of delivering ecosystem services – now embedded within ‘nature’s contributions to people (NCP)’ – and nature-based solutions. Evidence of these indirect economic outcomes is likely to be particularly challenging to produce if their evaluation is not planned in advance of a translocation. Economic losses include direct costs (e.g. damage to property, loss of crops or livestock), indirect costs (e.g. practice change and subsequent extra costs) and opportunity costs (e.g. missed opportunities from alternative scenarios). Economic costs and benefits are unlikely to be evenly distributed among stakeholders, nor (like all outcomes discussed here) will they necessarily remain stable. For example, ecotourism focusing on a translocated population may become less successful if the species becomes more widely established, and initial damage caused by translocated animals may be mitigated by adaptive management.

3.5. Ethical, Affective, and Philosophical

Even if implicit, all conservation translocations have ethical, affective and philosophical dimensions that underpin the more outcome-oriented motivations outlined above.

Motivations: Conservation and environmentalism are normative movements informed by a range of associated ethical and social values. The position that humans have a responsibility to move species from one place to another for conservation purposes is ultimately an ethical one (Arts et al. 2012), and translocations are initiated because people (as individuals or groups) seek to realise specific visions of nature (Deary and Warren 2019). Conservation contains multiple co-existing and sometimes competing philosophical and ideological paradigms (Sandbrook et al. 2019). This can produce disagreements between, for example, those who seek to translocate species to re-establish a historical species assemblage, those who would translocate a species to perform a particular ecological function (IUCN/SSC 2013; Blythe and Jepson 2020; Holmes et al. 2020), and those who might translocate a species as ‘assisted colonisation’ in the face of climate change. Divergent ideologies within conservation communities have emerged as challenges to reintroduction programmes in the form of a preference for natural recolonisation (Soorae 2018), a propensity for non-intervention, and scepticism towards reintroductions (Soorae 2013, 2016). Shared or divergent philosophies of nature and how it should be governed can also inspire social movements and activism (e.g. ‘guerrilla rewilding’) that may include unauthorised species translocations (Greenfield et al. 2025; Whitehead 2025), which in turn have effects on the success or popularity of initiatives at organisational and governmental levels.

CASE 3: TRANSLOCATION OF GREY WOLVES *CANIS LUPUS* IN MINNESOTA, USA

The case of the (at the time) proposed reintroduction of wolves *Canis lupus* on Isle Royale, Michigan, highlights the underlying pivotal role of ethical and philosophical motivations. In the early 2010s, the wolf population in the Isle Royale National Park (IRNP) severely declined a few decades after its arrival. Authors have attributed this to various factors including climate change reducing ice bridge connectivity with land, humans introducing a canine disease, lack of genetic diversity affecting wolf morphology, and other ecological dynamics (Vucetich et al. 2012, 2013; Cochrane 2013; Gostomski 2013; Mech 2013). A debate over reinforcing the population through translocation ensued. Contrary to other translocation contexts characterised by stakeholder conflicts (e.g. Yellowstone National Park), controversy centred on human intervention in ‘wilderness’ and approaches to implementation, which were rooted in different ethical and philosophical ideas about whether or not to translocate wolves. Non-intervention, the preference to let ‘nature run its course’, was associated with (a) the

idea that naturalness (Cochrane 2013) and wilderness (Gostomski 2013) were not strictly associated with the wolf population and its rescue and (b) the precautionary principle, to ensure ecosystem health and further unaltered research inquiry (Mech 2013). This contrasted with a more active conservation approach rooted in a belief in the essential socio-ecological role of wolves in ensuring ecosystem integrity and a belief that the wilderness concept must change in response to pervasive global human impacts (Vucetich et al. 2012, 2013). Each position largely depended on insufficient and uncertain information regarding human agency (i.e. whether and to what extent human agency originally contributed to wolves arriving on the island, and therefore if recolonising wolves were a native or non-native species), the effects of inbreeding, and the role of wolves and moose in the Isle Royale system.

Affective motivations are best exemplified by conservation translocations inspired by compassion for individual animals or populations. The IUCN is currently developing guidance for responsible translocation of displaced organisms, which includes care, rehabilitation and release of wildlife affected (individually or at larger scales) by natural and anthropogenic disasters or persecution. Affective motivations also, however, affect conservation translocations, including anger or a sense of loss following the local extirpation of a species, or, in the case of unauthorised translocations, frustration at the slowness of formal procedures and political negotiations; this may be one reason behind the recent unauthorised releases of lynx *Lynx lynx* in the Scottish Highlands (Greenfield et al. 2025). Finally, translocations may be motivated by personal enthusiasms or appreciation of a certain species. Projects may be envisioned and fronted by committed and sometimes empowered individuals (e.g. through positions of responsibility and/or extensive land ownership) who have a passion for specific species or proactive conservation approaches, including translocations. These personal enthusiasms, together with other less positive personal drivers such as ego, or a desire to wield power, are rarely acknowledged as drivers of translocations, despite likely being central to the generation and delivery of multiple projects.

Outcomes: Ethical, affective and philosophical outcomes are much more nebulous and challenging to evaluate due to their immeasurability and, often, implicitness. Nevertheless, translocations (or attempted translocations) can influence people's affective responses, ethical principles, and environmental values.

Positive emotions such as gratification, joy, and happiness could result from socio-ecologically successful translocations, especially if driven by personal enthusiasm, appreciation of, and passion for, a certain species or taxon. Such emotions could also arise through the fulfilment of specific visions of nature and the achievement of conservation action that is perceived as ethically right. Emotions are likely not limited to interested practitioners but could be shared by other involved stakeholders and communities, especially if translocation processes were perceived as shared and legitimate. Nevertheless, it is essential to also consider negative affective responses arising among stakeholders and local communities – such as fear or distrust – given their critical role in shaping tolerance and coexistence with wildlife (Marino et al. 2020; Kansky and Kidd 2024).

Other potential outcomes in this category are the reinforcement or existing normative beliefs and paradigms within the conservation community, or the shaping of new ones, which could have broader implications for overall conservation practice and research. Ideological outcomes include the impact translocations, or attempted translocations, have on people's broader environmental values and principles. A translocation project may be evaluated as an indicator of progress in ecological restoration and conservation, for example, or (from a different perspective) serve as a marker of outside interference and/or unwanted change in a landscape.

4. APPLYING THE FRAMEWORK

4.1. Project Conception

Decision-makers, managers, practitioners, and other stakeholders should actively and intentionally examine the proximate and ultimate motivations of their translocation programmes from the outset. Proximate motivations are those that provide the immediate justifications for translocations. As per current practice, these motivations are mostly ecological, often concerning the survival, expansion, and establishment of reintroduced populations. Increasingly, however, socio-cultural motivations are acknowledged as central to some projects, for example, restoring a species that is not of conservation concern but has cultural significance or potential to generate public interest (e.g. White et al. 2023). Ultimate motivations are the ‘final causes’ of conservation translocations. For example, translocations might be sought by societies to restore an ecological function or protect a species from extinction, by governments to achieve biodiversity targets, by organisations to generate support for conservation, and by individuals to champion a favoured species.

Identifying and acknowledging all relevant motivations can support project design by enabling practitioners to (a) set project aims and success criteria that fully and transparently reflect the nature of the project; (b) conduct initial assessments of translocation proposals that include a broader range of possible impacts (positive and negative); and (c) design projects in a more well-rounded way.

Considering the full scope of potential motivations and outcomes will highlight areas requiring particular focus and lead to project- and species-appropriate and balanced processes, particularly in terms of stakeholder engagement, whilst promoting a holistic approach to monitoring and outcome evaluation.

Motivations for initiating a translocation might differ between, and among, proponent organisations and individuals, stakeholder groups, and interested or affected communities due to different ideologies and values. Failing to acknowledge important motivations has the potential to jeopardise outcomes and generate distrust or conflict if, for example, some parties perceive translocations as an imposition of others’ visions of what constitutes a desirable outcome or public good.

Motivations should therefore be considered holistically, recognising that these span different dimensions and are interconnected. A holistic approach facilitates decision-making throughout the project cycle, where adequate planning, monitoring and evaluation connect each project motivation with its related aim-action-outcome strand and their interactions. This is particularly important as some motivations and aims may conflict with one another. For instance, the political motivation to achieve an environmental target might lead to definitions of timescales not adequate for the restoration of endangered populations and ecological processes).

Figure 2. An updated version of the conservation translocation cycle (IUCN/SSC 2013) highlighting key processes (green circles) underpinning the PaCT framework. Here, acknowledging proximate and ultimate motivations and enabling stakeholder participation are key processes that should contribute, respectively, to informing translocation aims, and feed back into project design, monitoring, evaluation and dissemination.

4.2. Planning and Implementation

Project planning and implementation should adequately reflect the motivations underlying the translocation. Motivations should be considered in relation to socio-political contexts to inform realistic and legitimate aims. For instance, the national political landscape may be well-suited to specific aims and provide ‘windows of opportunity’ for translocations to proceed (e.g. a pro-environmental government). In a local context, certain aims might fit current levels of cultural acceptance, sense of place, and willingness to restore/shape new cultural heritages, identities, intergenerational legacies and existing on-the-ground politics (e.g. current stakeholder relationships). Conversely, a lack of contextual awareness or sensitivity can result in clumsy communications or can reignite latent conflicts. For example, if a new translocation project is proposed in a region where previous projects have failed.

Initial planning should consist of developing a list of project options with their goals, advantages and disadvantages, opportunity costs, counterfactual (‘do-nothing’) risks, and outcomes. Frameworks and methodologies to help assess social feasibility and develop translocation plans are available and include decision trees and structured decision-making (Table 1). Decision thresholds should be included from the outset of a project, with go/no-go and abort points reflecting key elements of social feasibility such as sufficient or insufficient levels of tolerance for a translocated species, support for a project, or trust between stakeholders. This might help avoid sunk-cost fallacies and foster acceptance of the need to temporarily suspend or terminate projects if necessary. Overall, translocation planning and management might benefit from the integration of the *renewed coexistence* concept (Auster et al. 2022a), which encourages future-oriented consideration of coexistence issues in relation to conservation translocations.

Evaluation should be set up during the planning phase. Project managers should identify intended outcomes and consider possible *unintended* outcomes, their likelihood, evaluation, and possible solutions. Anticipating these early may prevent subsequent conflicts or challenges. Existing guidelines already include the key factors that should be

considered (e.g. in terms of social impacts of translocations) and recommended approaches to stakeholder participation and engagement. Stakeholders can be defined as the communities, organisations, bodies, and individuals whose interests might affect and/or be affected by a translocation programme. When a translocation is likely to directly impact stakeholder interests, plans should include an assessment of the need for mitigation and management solutions as well as measures to encourage coexistence such as financial incentives (e.g. conservation payments), privately funded compensation, and insurance schemes. These solutions require careful consideration in relation to impact mitigation as well as the responsibility relationships that they entail. For example, stakeholders are more likely to favour measures perceived as equitable, co-developed and co-owned (Dickman et al. 2011; IUCN 2023; Hamm et al. 2024).

Evaluation planning should also involve defining timeframes against which outcomes should be expected and evaluated. These may reflect other project milestones (e.g. funding and reporting deadlines, ecological indicators), yet some potential outcomes may need dedicated prediction and forecasting. By way of example, a reintroduced predator may not come into conflict with people until its population has reached critical size or density (see Case 2). Evaluation planning should therefore be able to respond to a range of scenarios, including uncertain long-term outcomes and delayed or failed translocations.

Stakeholder involvement and ownership

Different degrees of stakeholder involvement (*sensu* Luyet et al. 2012) exist, ranging from basic information sharing to empowerment, with consultation, collaboration, and co-decision in between. The degree of stakeholder involvement required should be established in advance during project appraisal or adapted appropriately during project planning. Any degree of involvement and use of participatory processes is likely to shape project ownership: ownership should be clearly established and communicated from the project’s outset. Any stakeholder involved in a translocation should also be acknowledged according to their degree of involvement.

Communication

Effectively communicating motivations, and how these relate to aims and measures of success, is important for several reasons. First, transparency and honesty around motivations and justifications enable meaningful engagement and build trust during consultations and feasibility studies. Second, clarifying aims and how they will be achieved supports the production of a well-rounded plan and (where required) a more robust licensing application. Third, reference to predetermined motivations and aims can help explain the project's approach to implementation or management during delivery and can support a suitable exit strategy when needed. In addition to motivations and aims, a communication strategy should cover the following critical aspects:

Background to the project. This involves explaining the history, status, and threats of targeted species. It should be made clear why a species is no longer present at the intended release area, if it was formerly resident, and if/how the situation has changed since its disappearance.

Evidence. Project communication should explicitly refer to the evidence used to support the decision-making process and the reasons why such evidence was chosen (e.g. useful lessons from similar translocations). Evidence that potentially challenges or contradicts the decision should also have been considered, and the strategy should acknowledge this (or, if excluding it, should be prepared to justify this if necessary).

Ownership, power dynamics, funding and timing.

Communication strategies should include unambiguous messaging concerning project funding sources, and ownership and roles among stakeholders to prevent misunderstanding and relationship damage.

Translocations are often bound to tight timelines due to an urgent need for action and time-limited funding opportunities. Being able to explain time and resource availability and scarcity to stakeholders can help manage expectations around potential outcomes.

Overall, some of the key questions underpinning communication strategies for translocations should be:

1. Why is this species being chosen?
2. What are the proximate and ultimate motivations and aims of the project?
3. Why here, and why now?
4. Who is responsible for what aspect of the project?

Translocation plans should be communicated using approaches, language and terminology suited to the target audience. An important feature of any communication approach is to ensure transparency and consistency throughout the translocation. This approach would include:

1. Being empathic and open to different reactions;
2. Managing expectations;
3. Avoiding exaggeration of benefits and underplaying risks;
4. Being consistent in core messaging.

Language and terminology are important when communicating translocations, from the initial drivers to the final outcomes. Certain species might have a strong cultural significance and be strongly associated with a particular language which, in turn, could be the best means of communicating. The right language could also become a 'tool' for advocacy and help projects to gain traction. Similarly, it should be recognised that terms such as 'rewilding', 'wilderness', and 'natural' have multiple and subjective meanings and inescapably connect projects to wider social discourses and debates, thus creating a misperception of diverging values between translocation proponents and recipients that, ultimately, might harm projects (Dando et al., 2025).

Communication can be delivered both internally and externally to the project. Translocation proponents should communicate with stakeholders (e.g. individuals, steering and advisory groups) by ensuring open and accessible multidirectional communication channels, for example, through multi-stakeholder team composition (Marino et al. 2024). This would allow proponents and stakeholders to share written plans, concerns, and advice as well as arrange regular participatory activities (e.g. review meetings). An internal communication approach might foster sharing self-reflections on motivations, for example, in the form of positionality statements. Assistance from independent facilitators can also enable constructive conversations with stakeholders early on, particularly in contexts with histories of conservation or wildlife management conflicts.

Lastly, a communication strategy should consider recipients outside the project itself, including careful consideration of the media environment. While press and social media responses to a project cannot (and should not) be controlled, external communications can be managed, and practitioners can ensure that stakeholders are informed of key milestones or challenges prior to their public release.

4.3. Monitoring

Once drivers, goals, and success criteria have been set during the planning stage, evidence can be collected in relation to linked outcomes. Monitoring should be a multi-stage process that enables an effective adaptive management approach and, ultimately, successful evaluation. First, monitoring should include pre-release baseline information that, for example, might be collected through engagement and consultation. Monitoring efforts should then continue iteratively during the implementation stage to inform project management in relation to social dimensions (e.g. development of trust or conflict between stakeholders and human-wildlife interactions).

Monitoring is a critical link between project planning, implementation, and evaluation. Throughout a project, monitoring should generate information relevant to and consistent with the identified motivations, goals and success indicators, suited to subsequent evaluation methods, and integrated into any decision-making framework adopted. Monitoring may enable adaptive management, allowing practitioners to broaden the scope of evaluation in projects that have been initiated with relatively narrow considerations of social dimensions. As with other elements of conservation translocations, monitoring can also be a collaborative and participatory process. Not only can this be instrumental to stakeholder engagement and information sharing, but it can also contribute to the inclusion of the multiple perspectives that are needed to produce holistic project evaluations.

5. EVALUATING OUTCOMES

Conservation translocations can have pervasive and transformative socio-ecological outcomes, even long after the release stage. Translocation projects therefore need to include appropriate evaluation to determine the success of the translocation and enable learning within and beyond the specific project. Our expanded framework enables the ‘Social, Cultural and Economic’ outcomes (IUCN/SSC 2013) to be more thoroughly reported, by breaking these down into outcomes that are political and strategic, socio-cultural, or economic, recognising their ethical, affective or philosophical underpinnings, and linking them back clearly to project aims. A robust evaluation programme should cover both (a) original project aims and (b) additional issues arising during implementation.

5.1. Identifying Outcomes

The aims of a project are its ‘intended outcomes’, and their success can be evaluated using our expanded framework (Figure 1). The framework can also be used to identify and classify additional or unexpected outcomes arising during, or following, a translocation. All outcomes might be evaluated as positive or negative in relation to their effect on the proximate and/or ultimate aims of the project. Practitioners should also adopt a reflective evaluation of project mechanisms/processes, rather than focus solely on external outcomes. Understanding from the inside how translocations are conducted is essential to improve decision-making, management, and overall practice (Marino et al. 2024b).

5.2. Approaches to evaluating non-ecological dimensions

A wide range of evaluation methods exist in the scientific literature and each one might or might not be suited to evaluate certain outcomes, at certain times and at certain scales. Table 1 provides a detailed list of the methods that evaluators such as conservation practitioners, stakeholders, and academics can use in their assessments. Given the wide range of potential outcomes outlined above, evaluation methods can be drawn from diverse disciplines and epistemologies. A range of methods can be used to investigate potential non-ecological outcomes such as stakeholder relationships and collaboration, health and wellbeing, or human-wildlife coexistence including social network analyses, surveys, discourse analyses, and interviews. Evaluation approaches can be simple and quick, but also multi-dimensional and mixed, deploying both qualitative and quantitative methods at a given point in time (cross-sectional) or repeatedly through time and project stages (longitudinal). For example, qualitative methods can be used to gather in-depth knowledge of a socio-ecological system from which quantitative surveys can be developed that can be repeated over time and with a larger sample.

5.3. Evaluation as a collaborative and participatory process

In view of the wide range of potential non-ecological outcomes from translocations, evaluation requires interdisciplinary expertise and the contribution of multiple evaluators. Consistent with planning and monitoring stages, diverse stakeholders should make a significant contribution to project evaluation (Marino et al. 2024b). These might be local stakeholders officially involved in translocations as members of advisory groups, or wider publics. Such contributions, although potentially difficult to obtain, should not be seen as a hurdle to project completion. Local communities are the ultimate recipients of conservation translocations and their outcomes. Therefore, similarly to the initial project design stages, they should be involved in evaluating translocation outcomes (Figure 2), even, indeed especially, where their perspectives might diverge from those of conservation practitioners. Upon establishing legitimacy and ownership, stakeholders and local communities could take over responsibility for monitoring and evaluation in the long term.

Evaluation can be also conducted in partnership with, or outsourced to, external evaluators such as academic institutions and consultants. This will, of course, depend on team capacity, capabilities, and funding. For example, when sharing evaluation efforts, project officers might initially investigate outcomes associated with the local context, and academic researchers might then scale-up the investigation by implementing quantitative approaches at a higher level. Furthermore, data associated with certain outcomes might not be available or difficult to gather for practitioners. In this case, external support might be necessary. For example, where relevant, economic outcomes, across their dimensions (scale, distribution, persistence), could be evaluated with support from consultants.

Table 1. Breakdown of methodologies (based on Bennett et al., 2017) suited to evaluate translocation drivers and outcomes, along with example from the scientific literature. Examples are arranged based on the release stage, the category of social outcomes and the main methods used along with any additional methods (in brackets).

Methodology	Drivers and outcome category	Reintroduction stage	Research examples
Planning and forward-thinking Scenario planning, structured-decision making, back-casting, visioning, economic modelling	All categories	Project planning and driver evaluation	
Qualitative Interviews (structured, semi-structured), survey, focus groups, participant observation, discourse and textual analysis, document analysis, free lists and pile sorts, ethnographies, photo elicitation, institutional analysis, case studies, comparative analysis, image analysis. Historical: Archival research, landscape histories, oral histories, historical geographic information system	Socio-cultural: Species acceptance and tolerance; human-wildlife interactions; relational values; nature connectedness; attitudes and behaviour; engagement, support; ownership, stewardship, accountability; relationships and trust, communication, collaboration/conflict, social learning; sense of community and social capital, social groups outreach; social trends, cultural heritage and reawakening; cultural respect; social acceptance. Political and strategic Political support/opposition; policy change; meeting legal commitments achieving biodiversity targets reputational gain/damage. Ethical, affective and philosophical Values; relation to and conceptualisation of nature; emotions.	Outcome monitoring and evaluation	Pre-release Socio-cultural Semi-structured interviews • Reading and Kellert 1993 (survey) • Schoenecker and Shaw 1997 • Langin and Jacobson 2012 (survey, regression analysis) • Lopes-Fernandes et al. 2018 (content analysis, ethnographic approach) • Marino et al. 2024a (participant observation) <i>Survey</i> • Pate et al. 1996 • Nilsen et al. 2007 <i>Structured interviews</i> • Caruso and Pérez 2013 <i>Participation Action Research</i> • Johnson et al. 2023 Socio-cultural and Ethical, affective and philosophical <i>Semi-structured interviews</i> • Lopes-Fernandes and Frazão-Moreira, 2017 (content analysis, ethnographic approach) Post-release Socio-cultural <i>Survey</i> • Bath et al. 2008 (Anova) • Auster et al. 2020a (semi-structured interviews) • Auster et al. 2020b (ordinary least squares regression/Anova) • Auster et al. 2022b (thematic analysis) • White et al. 2023 (thematic and text analysis) <i>Semi-structured interviews</i> • Coz and Young 2020 (thematic analysis) • Auster et al. 2021 (thematic analysis) • O'Rourke 2014 (media analysis)
Mixed Q-methodology Discourse network analysis	Socio-cultural (as above) Political and strategic (as above)		Pre-release Socio-cultural <i>Q methodology</i> • Bavin et al. 2020 • Hawkins et al. 2020 (questionnaire and thematic analysis) • Auster et al. 2022a • Bavin et al. 2023 • Auster et al. 2024 Socio-cultural and Political <i>Discourse network analysis</i> • Marino et al. 2023

Methodology	Drivers and outcome category	Reintroduction stage	Research examples
Quantitative Surveys, economic valuation, cost-benefit analysis, modelling, lab and field experiments, physiological evaluation, scanner data gathering	Socio-cultural (as above) Economic Willingness to pay; income levels, new investment opportunities; economic inequality; nature-based solutions. Political and strategic (as above) Ethical, affective and philosophical (as above)	Outcome monitoring and evaluation	Pre-release Socio-cultural <i>Survey</i> • Grima et al. 2021 (expert interviews, Pearson's chi squared test) • Niemiec et al. 2020 (regression analysis); • Sakurai et al. 2020 (regression analysis and text mining) • White et al. 2023 (Mann-Whitney U tests, generalised linear regression analysis) • Bath and Engel 2019 (cognitive hierarchy framework) Socio-cultural and Economic <i>Survey</i> • Ma et al. 2016 (Contingent Evaluation Method, regression analyses) • Moran and Lewis 2014 (semi-structured interviews) • Hamilton and Moran 2015 • Gaywood et al. 2015 Political <i>Survey</i> • Ditmer et al. 2022 (spatial linear regression analysis) Post-release Socio-cultural <i>Survey</i> • Schroeder et al. 2018 (regression mediation analysis) • Cervený et al. 2019 • Watkins et al. 2021 (structural equation modelling) • Martins et al. 2022 • Delibes-Mateos et al. 2022 (V Cramer and Anova, longitudinal study) • Holmes et al. 2024 Economic <i>Survey</i> • Chapagain and Poudyal 2020 (travel cost method) • Watkins and Poudyal 2021 (factor analyses and binomial logistic regression); • Notaro and Grilli 2021 Notaro and Grilli 2021 (discrete choice experiment) Ethical, Affective and Philosophical <i>Survey</i> • Hiroyasu et al. 2019; Hiroyasu et al. 2019
Participatory Group facilitation methods (nominal groups, Delphi processes), community-based research (traditional calendars, group ranking), participatory action research, art-based methods (photovoice, participatory videography)	Socio-cultural (as above) Political and strategic (as above) Ethical, affective and philosophical (as above)	Outcome monitoring and evaluation	
Evaluative Monitoring and evaluation (e.g., randomised control trials, synthetic counterfactual, most significant change, process tracing, realistic evaluation), policy analysis, argument analysis, case analysis, statutory interpretation	All categories	Outcome monitoring and evaluation	

6. LEARNING AND SHAPING NEW CONSERVATION POLICY AND PRACTICE

The aim of evaluation processes is to improve collective knowledge, practice, and policy. Therefore, all evaluation outputs should be shared, ideally in open-access repositories, regardless of the overall success or failure of a project and its specific outcomes.

Consistent with the communication strategy, reporting should be done transparently, in recognition of underlying motivations and intended aims but also with care and respectfully of involved and recipient stakeholders, and especially in case of failure, unintended and/or negative outcomes. Although not common, informative examples of failed attempts can be found in the grey literature among the IUCN Global Reintroduction Perspectives and, for example within the UK, among the Back from the Brink project reports (e.g. Narrow-headed ant reintroduction). For example, the attempted reintroduction of red squirrels *Sciurus vulgaris* in the Purbeck Peninsula (Dorset), which was part of a methodology development approach associated within regional grey squirrel *Sciurus carolinensis* eradication, offered insights into the interconnections between suboptimal habitat, dispersal, predation, interspecific competition and disease (Shuttleworth et al. in Soorae 2016).

At the local level, evaluation outputs can be shared through specialist groups, fora, and advisory body regional chairs. Projects should also be enabled to report to and inform centralised translocation/reintroduction hubs and taskforces at a national level (where these exist). Through sharing and transferability, this body of information can shape future best practice guidance. Ultimately, evaluation and information-sharing might drive policy change, leading to new legislation and frameworks to protect socio-ecological systems through more successful conservation translocations.

7. CONCLUSION

Conservation translocations are fundamentally human endeavours that, as well as achieving ecological objectives, can also have social, political, and economic motivations and outcomes. This framework provides a structured approach to identifying and evaluating the full spectrum of motivations and outcomes associated with translocation projects. The framework emphasises the importance of clarity and transparency about the motivations underpinning translocation proposals; linking specific aims to intended outcomes; and systematic evaluation of those outcomes. It highlights that social dimensions of translocations extend beyond stakeholder consultation and impact mitigation and recommends meaningful stakeholder engagement throughout the project lifecycle. Employing this framework alongside existing guidelines will support more holistic project planning, robust evaluation processes, and ultimately more successful conservation outcomes.

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